

Pressure Dependency of Conductivity Measurements: The Specific Case of the Lung

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Abstract: In this paper, we examined how the applied pressure influences the measurement of conductivity in lung tissue. We found that the conductivity of lung increases with increased pressure. The increase in conductivity can be explained by the air being pushed out of the lung under the applied pressure.

1 Introduction

The electrical conductivity of tissues at low frequencies is fundamental for medical electromagnetic applications, such as electrical impedance tomography. There are several studies in the literature reporting conductivity measurements of lung. However, knowledge of this data at frequencies below 100 kHz is limited due to measurement challenges. One of the challenges is the pressure dependency of the conductivity in soft tissue. Moqadam *et al.* [2] found that each type of tissue responds differently to compression, where the slopes of the conductivity-pressure plots differed between the tested tissues. Dodde *et al.* [1] explained the change in conductivity due to the applied pressure by changes to the electrolyte or fluid volume in the tissue. Under tissue compression, pressure gradients developed within the tissue and act to drive fluid out of both the intra- and extracellular spaces [1]. This results in decreased conductivity with added pressure intra- and extracellular fluids contain electrolytes that mostly contribute to the overall conductivity of the tissue. Lung tissue is a specific case in that it is filled with air and by compressing the tissue, we also deflate the lung. Gabriel *et al.* [3] treated the inflated and the deflated lung separately, finding a lower conductivity for the inflated lung (0.042 S/m for inflated lung and 0.11 S/m for deflated lung). Given that air is much less conductive than the lung tissue, it is expected the conductivity increases as the air is expelled from the lung. This study aims to determine which one of the two effects, the increase in conductivity due to the air being expelled or the decrease in conductivity due to the liquid being expelled, is going to be more significant in impacting the conductivity

2 Methods

In this experiment, we performed the measurements on ovine lung that was acquired by the local abattoir. The lung was placed on a weighing scale under the probe. The weighing scale was zeroed before the probe made contact with the lung tissue. The probe was then brought into contact with the tissue and the pressure was monitored on the weighing scale (via applied force). We performed 10 measurements, changing the force (and consequently the pressure) from 1 N to 10 N. The acquisition of the complex impedance at five different frequencies ($f = 10$ Hz, 100 Hz, 1kHz, 10 kHz and 100 kHz) was performed using the methods described in [4] with a PGSTAT204 galvanostat (Metrohm Autolab B.V., Utrecht, The Netherlands) and a custom four-

electrode probe.

Fig. 1 shows the results of the measurements at $f = 1$ kHz. The conductivity increases as the pressure is increasing. This can be explained by the fact that under the applied pressure, the air is pushed out of the lung. Since the air acts as a near perfect electric insulator, when it's pushed out of the lung, the increase in conductivity is expected. The same trend is observed at the other frequencies.

Figure 1: The measured conductivity of lung versus the applied pressure ($f = 1$ kHz). The conductivity increases as the pressure increases. This finding can be explained by the air being pushed out of the lung.

3 Conclusions

This study shows that lung tissue conductivity increases with the pressure. This is unlike other tissues for which the conductivity decreases. This effect is in contrast with the usual effect of decreasing conductivity with pressure due to the liquid being pushed out of the tissue. The different behaviour can be explained by the fact that the conductivity of lung tissue depends on the amount of air in the tissue, which is not the case for other tissue types.

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